

Figure 6A: P-S6 Film

P-S6

Figure 6A Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: **Sib-2 Veh**, Lane 2: Sib-2: SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 3: **Sib-2 MK-2206 (10 nM)**

Lane 4: **I-ASD-2 Veh**, Lane 5: I-ASD-2 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 6: I-ASD-2: MK-2206 (10 nM)

Bolded text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 6A: GAPDH for PS6 Film (TOP), GAPDH for Total S6 film (bottom)

Figure 6A Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Phospho
GAPDH

Lane 1: **Sib-2 Veh**, Lane 2: Sib-2: SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 3: **Sib-2 MK-2206 (10 nM)**
Lane 4: **I-ASD-2 Veh**, Lane 5: I-ASD-2 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 6: I-ASD-2: **MK-2206 (10 nM)**
Bolded text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 6A Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Total
GAPDH

Lane 1: **Sib-2 Veh**, Lane 2: Sib-2: SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 3: **Sib-2 MK-2206 (10 nM)**
Lane 4: **I-ASD-2 Veh**, Lane 5: I-ASD-2 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 6: I-ASD-2: **MK-2206 (10 nM)**
Bolded text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

Figure 6A: Total S6 film

Figure 6A Arrows indicate lanes utilized in figure

Lane 1: **Sib-2 Veh**, Lane 2: Sib-2: SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 3: **Sib-2 MK-2206 (10 nM)**
Lane 4: **I-ASD-2 Veh**, Lane 5: I-ASD-2 SC-79 (6ug/mL), Lane 6: **I-ASD-2: MK-2206 (10 nM)**

Bolded text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows